

References

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R = H, acyl or alkyl
R' = H or alkyl
X = O or H₂

Antifungal activity: *In vitro* antifungal activity was determined by a two fold serial dilution method⁴ against *T. mentagrophytes*, *M. canis*, *C. neoformans* and *H. capsulatum*; amphotericin B being selected for serving as the sensitivity control.

The minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) expressed as mcg/ml of the different pyridazines (II) are shown in Table 1.

Experimental

2,3,4,4a-Tetrahydro-3-oxo-5H-indeno[1,2-c]pyridazine (I): A mixture of ethyl 1-oxo-indan-2-ylacetate (14 g, 0.075 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (80%, 6.3 ml) was refluxed in alcohol for 6 hrs. Alcohol was distilled off and the residual yellow material crystallised (charcoal) from boiling water to give (I) in colourless plates (9.0 g, 76%), m.p. 188°; ν (Nujol) 3250 (NH), 1680 cm^{-1} (amide CO); PMR (CDCl_3): τ 6.5-8 (m, 5H, $\text{CH}_2\text{-CH-CH}_2$); 2.1-2.7 (m, 4H, ArH); 0.75 (s, 1H NH). In presence of D_2O the peak at τ 0.75 disappeared.

1,2,3,4,4a,9b-Hexahydro-3-oxo-5H-indeno [1,2-c]pyridazine (II, R=R'=H, X=O): The above pyridazine (I) (11.2 g, 0.06 mol) dissolved in absolute alcohol (100 ml) was hydrogenated at 45 lbs pressure of hydrogen with the addition of 3 drops of concentrated HCl and palladium charcoal (0.5 g, 10%). After consumption of theoretical amount of hydrogen, the catalyst was filtered out, alcohol distilled off completely, and the product (II, R=R'=H, X=O) crystallised from benzene-light petroleum in fine needle shaped crystals (10.5 g, 91%), m.p. 169-170°; ν (Nujol) 3250, 3350 (NH), 1680 cm^{-1} (amide CO). [Found: C, 70.6; H, 6.1; N, 14.71. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires C, 70.2; H, 6.38; N, 14.84%].

Synthesis of Indeno [1,2-c] Pyridazines as Possible Antifungal Agents

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TAKAHASHI and co-workers^{1,2} observed high *in vitro* antimycotic activity in some arylpyridazines. Again, high *in vitro* antifungal activity of undec-10-enylindan hydrochloride was also demonstrated³. So it was considered worthwhile to synthesize some indeno-pyridazine derivatives (II) and to investigate their antifungal activity, if any.

Ethyl 1-oxo-indan-2-ylacetate was condensed with hydrazine to give the pyridazine (I). This structure was ascertained by its pmr spectrum. It was hydrogenated to [II, R=R'=H, X=O]. The latter was acylated with undec-10-enoic acid chloride to give the amide [II, R=CO(CH₂)₉CH=CH₂, R'=H, X=O], the amide functions of which were reduced with LAH and the resultant hexahydroindeno-pyridazine [II, R=(CH₂)₉CH=CH₂, R'=H, X=H₂] was further alkylated.

TABLE 1—ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY OF THE PYRIDAZINES (II)

Sl. No.	R	R'	X	Minimum <i>in vitro</i> inhibitory concn. (mcg/ml)			
				<i>T. mentagrophytes</i>	<i>M. canis</i>	<i>C. neoformans</i>	<i>H. capsulatum</i>
1.	H	H	O	n	n	n	n
2.	CO(CH ₂) ₉ CH=CH ₂	H	O	n	n	n	n
3.	(CH ₂) ₉ CH=CH ₂	H	H ₂	50	n	12.5	12.5
4.	(CH ₂) ₉ CH=CH ₂	CH ₃	H ₂	50	25	n	n
5.	(CH ₂) ₉ CH=CH ₂	C ₂ H ₅	H ₂	100	12.5	n	n
6.	(CH ₂) ₉ CH=CH ₂	n-C ₃ H ₇	H ₂	50	n	n	100
7.	Amphotericin B	—	—	6.25	0.25	1.0	0.5

n = no activity upto 100 mcg/ml.

1-(Undec-10-enyl)-1,2,3,4,4a,9b-hexahydro-3-oxo-5H-Indeno [1,2-c] pyridazine [II, R=CO(CH₂)₉CH=CH₂, R'=H, X=O]: To a solution of the foregoing compound (11.2 g, 0.06 mol) in a mixture of ethyl acetate (100 ml) and pyridine (7 g), undec-10-enoic acid chloride (12.1 g) was added dropwise under mechanical stirring at 25°. Stirring was continued for 10 hrs more, excess acid chloride decomposed with water and organic layer separated and washed successively with water, dilute HCl (2N), NaOH (2N) solution and water. The usual processing afforded the desired pyridazine (14.9 g, 70%), m.p. 113-114° (light petroleum); ν (Nujol) 3200 (NH), 1660 cm⁻¹ (amide CO). [Found: C, 82.7; H, 8.3; N, 7.9. C₂₂H₃₀N₂O₂ requires C, 82.4; H, 7.9; N, 8.4%].

1-(11-Undec-10-enyl)-1,2,3,4,4a,9b-hexahydro-5H-Indeno [1,2-c] pyridazine [II, R=(CH₂)₉CH=CH₂, R'=H, X=H₂]: The above amide [II, R=CO(CH₂)₉CH=CH₂, R'=H, X=O] (10 g, 0.03 mol) dissolved in dry tetrahydrofuran (100 ml) was added dropwise to a solution of LAH (3.19 g, 0.09 mol) in THF (100 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 60 hrs, the THF was distilled off completely and the residue decomposed with water. The reaction mixture was extracted with benzene, the extract washed with water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of the solvent yielded the desired pyridazine (5.0 g, 50%), b.p. 200°/2 mm; ν 3400 cm⁻¹ (NH). [Found: C, 80.1; H, 10.9; N, 8.6. C₂₂H₃₄N₂ requires C, 80.09; H, 11.32; N, 8.59%].

1-(1-Undec-10-enyl)-2-alkyl-1,2,3,4,5a,4a,9b-hexahydro-5H-indeno [1,2-c] pyridazine [II, R=(CH₂)₉CH=CH₂, R=alkyl, X=H₂]: A mixture of the amine [II, R=(CH₂)₉CH=CH₂, R'=H, X=H₂; 1.0 g, 0.03 mol], formic acid (2.0 g, 0.04 mol, 90%) and formaldehyde (0.9 g of 40%, 0.012 mol) was heated in an oil bath at 100° for 10 hrs. Excess of formic acid and formaldehyde was removed by distillation. The contents were cooled and basified with ammonia. The liberated base was taken up in benzene and processed as usual to give the pyridazine [R=(CH₂)₉-CH=CH₂, R=CH₃, X=H₂] (0.4 g, 40%), b.p. 140°/1.5 mm.

A mixture of the amine [II, R=(CH₂)₉CH=CH₂, R'=H, X=H₂; 1.0 g, 0.003 mol] and ethyl bromide (0.4 g, 0.0033 mol) was heated on a water bath for 6 hrs. The product was basified with ammonia and processed as usual when the pyridazine [II, R=(CH₂)₉-CH=CH₂; R=C₂H₅, X=H₂] (0.4 g, 35%), b.p. 135-140°/2.5mm was obtained. The corresponding amine with R'=n-C₈H₁₇, b.p. 103°/1.5 mm was obtained in 60% yield. The above three compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis, and they did not show any NH absorption band in their ir spectra.

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Separation and Gravimetric Determination of Niobium and Tantalum with *N-o-Tolyl-p-Tertiarybutylbenzohydroxamic Acid***

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THE present paper describes the separation and gravimetric determination of niobium and tantalum with *N-o-tolyl-p-tertiarybutylbenzohydroxamic acid* (TTBBHA). The method is fairly selective and many of the common ions normally associated with niobium and tantalum do not interfere.

Experimental

N-o-Tolyl-p-tertiarybutylbenzohydroxamic acid was prepared by the reported method¹. Standard solutions of niobium and tantalum were prepared by the potassium bisulphate, tartaric acid fusion method of Schoeller² and the metal ion content was determined gravimetrically with cupferron³.

General procedure: A suitable aliquot of standard solution of niobium or tantalum was taken. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 4.0-6.0 for niobium and 0.5-1.5 for tantalum with 10% (v/v) sulphuric acid or 20% (w/v) ammonium acetate. The solution was heated to 60° and 10-20 ml of 2% reagent solution in alcohol was added slowly with constant stirring. The granular precipitate of niobium or tantalum was digested on a hot water bath for 45 minutes. The precipitates of niobium or tantalum complex were filtered, washed thoroughly with hot water and finally with 10% aqueous alcohol to remove traces of the reagent.

The precipitate of niobium complex was dried at 120° to constant weight and weighed as NbO·(C₁₃H₂₀O₂N)₃. The precipitate of tantalum complex was dried at 110° and ignited to pentoxide in a preweighed silica crucible and weighed as Ta₂O₅.

Properties and composition of niobium and tantalum complexes: The freshly precipitated niobium complex was white and crystalline. It was insoluble in water and 10% aqueous alcohol and slightly soluble in chloroform. The niobium complex was thermally

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